

Characterisation & prediction of failure in injection-moulded short-fibre composites

– from coupons to components –

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mecomposites

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AsahiKASEI

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Injection-moulded composites

Why?

Manufacturing process:

- Complex geometries
- Very short cycles & automated

Market:

- ~24% share of FRPs in value

Typical constituents:

- PA66 (thermoplastic) matrix
- Short glass fibres (~50% weight)

Large-volume applications

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Door mirror

Switch

Engine mount

Canister

Radiator tank

Head covers

Microstructure of injection-moulded composites

Microstructure of injection-moulded composites

Fibre orientation tensor

$$A(x, y, z) = \begin{bmatrix} a_{xx} = 0.0 & a_{xy} = 0 & a_{xz} = 0 \\ a_{xy} = 0 & a_{yy} = 1.0 & a_{yz} = 0 \\ a_{xz} = 0 & a_{yz} = 0 & a_{zz} = 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A(x, y, z) = \begin{bmatrix} a_{xx} = 0.5 & a_{xy} = 0 & a_{xz} = 0 \\ a_{xy} = 0 & a_{yy} = 0.5 & a_{yz} = 0 \\ a_{xz} = 0 & a_{yz} = 0 & a_{zz} = 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Microstructure of injection-moulded composites

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Effect of fibre orientation on mechanical properties

Effect of fibre orientation on mechanical properties

Young's modulus

Tensile strength

Failure strain

Simulation of injection moulding manufacturing process

Predicting fibre orientation tensor

- Polymer:
 - Rheology properties
 - Thermal properties
 - PVT
 - Mechanical properties
 - Fibres:
 - Aspect ratio
 - Thermal properties
 - Mechanical properties
- AsahiKASEI**

Skin
Core
Skin

Injection moulding conditions

Simulation of injection moulding manufacturing process

Predicting fibre orientation tensor

- Polymer:
- Rheology properties
 - Thermal properties
 - PVT
 - Mechanical properties
- Fibres:
- Aspect ratio
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- AsahiKASEI**

Injection moulding conditions

Validation

Material model dependent on local fibre orientation

Model identification

Fibres: • Elastic constants • Aspect ratio

Mori-Tanaka + Voigt
J2-plasticity
Tsai-Hill failure criterion

Matrix: • Elastic properties • Plasticity curve

UD composite: • Failure strains (longitudinal/transverse/shear)

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Verification

Coupled FEA: simulating manufacturing+structural response 6

Coupon scale

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Excellent agreement

Coupled FEA: simulating manufacturing+structural response ⁶

Coupon scale

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Real component: engine mount

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Lacking failure propagation?

Can we improve predictions for injection-moulded composites by considering progressive failure?

Composites Part B: Engineering

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Predicting failure in injection-moulded short-fibre subcomponents under varied environmental conditions through fracture mechanics

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Can we improve predictions for injection-moulded composites by considering progressive failure?

Fracture toughness testing

Compact tension specimens

Setup

Outputs

Load vs. displacement
Specimen compliance

Strain fields
J-integral

Crack growth
(visual)

Load vs. displacement curves

R-curves

Effect of fibre orientation

From specimen orientation...

Effect of fibre orientation

From specimen orientation...

... to fibre orientation

$$A(x, y, z) = \begin{bmatrix} a_{xx} & a_{xy} & a_{xz} \\ a_{xy} & a_{yy} & a_{yz} \\ a_{xz} & a_{yz} & a_{zz} \end{bmatrix}$$

Can we improve predictions for injection-moulded composites by considering progressive failure?

Setup

Setup

Results

Manufacturing simulation

Structural simulation

Top failure: effect of fibre orientation on fracture surface

Validation

Top failure: effect of fibre orientation on fracture surface

Conventional skin-core-skin partition

Validation

Top failure: effect of fibre orientation on fracture surface

Conventional skin-core-skin partition

Refined partition at top (initiation site)

Validation

Top failure: fracture surface formation

Experiments (fractography)

Stable failure initiation

Through-the-width propagation

Unstable through-the-thickness propagation

Simulations (stiffness degradation on fracture surface)

Weld-line failure: effect of properties of weld-line

Predicted fibre orientation

Weld-line failure: effect of properties of weld-line

Predicted fibre orientation

Validation

Weld-line failure: effect of properties of weld-line

Predicted fibre orientation

Validation

Weld-line failure: effect of properties of weld-line

Predicted fibre orientation

Validation

Weld-line failure: effect of properties of weld-line

Predicted fibre orientation

Validation

Conclusions

Can we improve predictions for injection-moulded composites by considering progressive failure?

Yes!

Proposed workflow

- Prediction of fibre orientations after injection moulding
- Fracture toughness measurements vs. fibre orientation
- Robust for different failure modes and complex geometries

Challenges ahead

- More refined representation of toughness vs. fibre orientation
- Improve representation of weld-lines
- Well-known challenges with simulating progressive failure

Conclusions

Can we improve predictions for injection-moulded composites by considering progressive failure?

Yes!

Effect of specimen orientation

Cohesive zone model identification

Fibre orientation on fracture surface

Toughness assignment

Assess robustness: effect of environmental conditions

Coupon experiments

Assess robustness: effect of environmental conditions

Coupon experiments

Subcomponent experiments

Assess robustness: effect of environmental conditions

Failure initiation cannot predict ultimate load

Accounting for **local** toughness increases accuracy

Core toughness **does** affect ultimate load if there is stable propagation

